

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B249
Date: 29 November 2006
Take Off: 10:52:52
Landing: 12:34:30
Flight Time: 1h41m38

Campaign: NEON

Operating Area: East Anglia and North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
9	IR Camera	James Bowles	Met Office
10	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office
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Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b249
 Date: 29/11/06
 Project: NEON
 Location: East Anglia and North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
104133		engine start	-.01 kft	127	
104413		power change	-.01 kft	127	
104533		taxy	-.01 kft	127	
105252		T/O	-.02 kft	211	
105316		heimann	0.39 kft	218	exposed
112716	114204	Profile 1	10.0 kft	223	
113758		Wattisham	2.3 kft	236	vis30km, wind=230 11kts
114731		bbr	0.77 kft	315	retract
115212	115347	Run 1.1	0.45 - 0.42 kft	047	heim cal at start
120447	120724	Run 2.1	0.46 - 0.51 kft	234	120650 abeam rwy 120714 abeam rwy end
120900		bbr	4.2 kft	006	extend
120935		heimann	5.4 kft	006	shuttered
123430		Land	-.04 kft	210	
123907		standstill	-.02 kft	000	

B249 Track 29-NOV-06

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight B249 (NEON flight during WINTEX)

29th. Nov 2006

Trial Objectives

To validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera looking at a runway.

- Almost identical to previous NEON sorties during VISURB and CAPEX, but without Heiman-ARIES-loops (as ARIES not available before Christmas)
- measurements under different (winter) atmospheric conditions intended

Take off

10:30 local

Location

Over and nearby a runway (Wattisham Airfield).

Weather

Ideally: Totally cloud free conditions, flights around lunch time.

Instrumentation Required

IR camera, core temperature, water vapour, Heiman, aerosol instruments (PCASP)

Special Conditions + Hints

- Note that in order to keep the runway in the field of view of the IR camera all altitudes will need to be flown at exact heights above the surface and not at flight levels.
- Try to get the same part of the runway in the FoV at every altitude.
- Try to keep a roughly constant roll angle (ideally near zero) when taking photos of runway or ships.
- Important: Get information on **ground-based visibility** at the time of profiling from the airfield

Flight Pattern (see Fig. 1)

1. Take off and transit to airfield/runway, to arrive at 10,000ft.
--- Over/nearby runway-----
2. 1st PROFILE = descent at 1,000ft/min to minimum altitude (if possible with a missed approach at the operating airfield)
3. Two runs at 500ft, sequence: over and along runway, loop, displaced to runway over grass/ravel path next to runway; Heiman to look down on runway or grass respectively
4. 20-degree approaches (see Fig. 3), i.e. straight and level runs at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, and 10,000ft (getting the runway into the field of view of the IR camera)
5. 2nd PROFILE, identical to point 2 (if possible include another missed approach at the operating airfield)
6. repeat point 3

7. [Extra tasks, e.g. search a larger ship (e.g. a tanker) + fly at altitudes of 1000, 3000, 5000 and 10000ft above the ship, thereby getting the ship in the field of view of the IR camera

8. Transit back.
9. Landing.

Total time: about 3 hours for NEON + extras

NEON Sortie WINTEX

V/P = "fast" vertical profile
M/A = missed approach over runway
HAL = "Heimann-ARIES loop"

Fig. 1: NEON sortie Height vs. Time. It includes:

- Two vertical profiles (scientific flying), if possible ending with missed approaches
- Several "20-degree approaches" (cp. Fig. 3) at 1000, 3000, 5000, and 10,000ft.
- The two HALs (Heiman-ARIES-loops, as flown at earlier NEON missions) were crossed out and are substituted by points 3 and 6 in the flight pattern description.
- "Extra Tasks": time can be used for whatever project to use the maximum flying time.

“20-degree approach” - top view -

Fig. 3: “20 degree approach” instead of flying parallel to the runway to get runway in FoV of the IR cam.

!!!! IR camera

- Get runway in FoV of the IR camera during the 20-degree approaches (cp. Fig. 3), check using spotter camera. **If this fails, run must be repeated!**
- Record both, IR camera and spotter camera pics.

Appendix A:

Height – Distance Conversion

The horizontal shift S of flight legs parallel to the runway to keep the runway in the view of the IR camera is dependent on the angle Y the camera is looking below the horizontal and the flight height H:

$$S \text{ (nautical miles)} = H \text{ (ft)} / \tan(Y) * 0.3048 * 0.54E-03$$

Assuming IR camera view = 35 degrees down the horizontal:

(Use EXCEL sheet to compute distances for other angles, <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/>)

Ideal NEON flight levels marked with an X	Flight Height (ft)	Displacement right of runway (nautical miles)	Flight Height (km)	Displacement (km)	Displacement (statute miles)	IR camera viewing distance (km)
missed approach: X	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	500	0.118	0.152	0.218	0.135	0.12
X	1000	0.235	0.305	0.435	0.270	0.53
	2000	0.470	0.610	0.871	0.541	
X	3000	0.705	0.914	1.306	0.811	1.59
	4000	0.940	1.219	1.741	1.082	
X	5000	1.175	1.524	2.176	1.352	2.66
	6000	1.410	1.829	2.612	1.623	
	7000	1.645	2.134	3.047	1.893	
	8000	1.880	2.438	3.482	2.164	4.25
	9000	2.115	2.743	3.918	2.434	
X	10000	2.350	3.048	4.353	2.705	5.31
	12000	2.821	3.658	5.224	3.246	
(X)	14000	3.291	4.267	6.094	3.787	7.44
	27000	6.346	8.230	11.753	7.303	

Table 1: Displacement for straight and level runs to keep the runway in the FoV of the IR camera (Y=35 degrees).

Fig. 4: Displacement graph (Y=35 degrees).

Mission scientist de-brief

B249 NEON flight
29th November 2006

Mission scientist: Clare Lee

Due to the IR camera having the incorrect focal setting the flight was terminated early. The flight had been set up to perform a NEON sortie over Wattisham airfield.

As fuel had to be burnt off before landing several of the sortie manoeuvres were performed. There were no clouds at all during the flight, just a low level haze layer. This exercise proved useful in identifying potential difficulties:

- Wattisham air traffic is particularly congested on Wednesday afternoons, in good weather conditions due, to gliding activities. There was the possibility of operating above 3000ft however.
- Heavy air traffic was also encountered due to helicopter operations. This is not restricted to Wednesday.
- Heimann calibrations must be started 2 minutes before the airfield overpass, whilst the aircraft maintains the specified fixed altitude.
- Core chemistry requires calibration of 3 minutes at each fixed altitude.

Instrument problems:

IR camera has incorrect focus position

Mission scientist laptop mouse is not working correctly.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B2489** Date **29/11/06** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:52:52					T10 Canfield Clear skies ^{above} w on horizon. Some haze. (T10 Delay due to nav. update being slow).
11:04:00		11000ft.	062	52°24'N / 12°0'E	Transit clear above. Haze on horizon + some haze below. IR camera not seeing clear picture - probability that not set to view so from contradiction between instructions verbal + written. Need to turn fuel ^{fuel} off before landing, here doing some of manoeuvres for practice.
11:27:16	P1 ↓	10000ft.	224		Profile descent into Wathisham Visibility from Wathisham: ^{cloud} 30km low level. ^{5 clear.} Wind: ^{ground} 220/11 ^{high level} 250/30 From air: clear with haze.
11:42:04	Pland	50ft.	225	52°6'N / 0°54'E	Over runway. - Wathisham 1017
11:52:12	R1.1	500ft.	048		Herman Isl. on towards runway. SW → NE straight down runway.
11:53:22				52°6' /	Over runway
11:53:43					end of runway
11:53:47	R1.1 ^{end} →	1000ft.			climb to turn around. Note lots of air traffic (helicopters).

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B249
Date of flight: 29/11/06

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B249
Date of Flight: 29/11/06

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer B249.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (B249.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B249.zip	y	Size of B249.dat = 1437760
6) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	Y	Blocks read =timed out
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B249.dat	Y	Blocks written =
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B249_seadas.dat	Y	Bad reads =0
WAVE> exit	Y	
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	Y	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B249_seadas.dat	Y	
d) Comment string:	Y	
e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i>	Y	Start = 0
f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i>	Y	End = 240000
g) Read 2DC: Y	Y	Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y	Y	(vestigial error from tapes)
i) Secondary data: Y	Y	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	Y	Are FRW, FSP, IMB,
k) cmd.str: Y	Y	PCA,SEC yes
l) Auto time correction: N	Y	files in PMSDATA?
m) Full length secondary: N	y	Are they non-zero in size? no
8) FLOODS> WAVE		2D image display and printing
i). WAVE> imagedisplay		Must be done from FLOODS itself.
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) File generation no: 0		
d) Time from IWC plot: N		
e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i>		
g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i>		
h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images)		
ii). WAVE> auto_image		Note any problems with images
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD		
d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i>		Start =
e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i>		End =
f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10		
iii). WAVE> exit to create files		FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_
iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps
v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		Notes on this in instructions
vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B249
Date of Flight: 29/11/06

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	Y	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	Y	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	Y	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	Y	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	Y	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	Y	
d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i>	y	Min size =1
<i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i>	Y	
	Y	
e) Calibration volume flow rate:		
<i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i>	Y	Vol flow rate = 1.8
<i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i>	Y	
<i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i>	Y	
f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i>	Y	
g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i>	Y	
h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	
3) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	Y	
ii). WAVE> exit	Y	
4) FLOODS> MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp		
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		X =a
c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY		Y = X+1 =b
d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		
5) CHECKS		
Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph blue scatter 765</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK? So little data I'm not sure.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 249

Date: 27 September 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann		Y	HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	N	
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	N		Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red		Y	CVI	N	
“ Pyrgeometer		Y			
“ JNO2	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer	Y	Y
“ Pyrgeometer	N		Filters	Y	Y
“ JNO2	N		AMS	N	
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
MARSS	N		CDP	Y	N
DEIMOS	N		SAW	Y	N
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2		N	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX		Y	ADA	N	N
CO		Y	CPI	N	N
ORAC	N	N	NOxy	N	
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	N	
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling	N	
WAS		N	Tube Sampling	N	

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B249

Date: 29 November 2006

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS U/S
2. Lower BBRs not connected at startup – remedied before flight
3. TWC flashed as expected on switch-on, source ready after a few minutes, but status light remains on – fault? Data are present!
- 4.

Aircraft

1. Sidewall near flight manager loose
- 2.

Satcom H Calls - Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 29/12/06

Flight No. 5249

Pre-Flighter: JT

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	Can't find it
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	CO flows a bit high gases on no power to racks
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	unclear about now
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	EFC rubbish aft + down no filter (hooked up to 112)
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT FITTED
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT ON EARLY Fit may be complete
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	4 th can't find breaker Windows 19
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	NOT USED JC
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			ethernet link from PC - to LAN on Neph messily
	<input type="checkbox"/>			look into making sooty log w/out Send to ethernet Co. →
External Checks overleaf				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	tally but new
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	nice & shiny no Pyrg. x2 Pyrg + clear
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	not fitted yet as of preflight
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

option 1 h-stop h-optic
 unloc
 reloc
 h-stop h-optic

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B249:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	No log available due to corrupt Word file.
Filters	Testing equipment only; no log taken
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log (except in cases of instrument problems)
IR Camera In Flight log	No IR Camera log was required due to technical problems.

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	17 Dec 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
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